

CREATING LEVERAGE TO ENHANCE BIODIVERSITY OUTCOMES
OF GLOBAL BIOMASS TRADE

Database on biomass trade, production, demand, biodiversity proxies

Deliverable 3.1

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Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY5

INTRODUCTION6

OBJECTIVES7

METHODS8

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION9

- 1. International trade network9
- 2. Biodiversity indicators10
- 3. Aquaculture expansion and trade17
- 4. Land tenure19
- 5. Supply chain governance20
- 6. Land supply elasticities23

CONCLUSION25

PROJECT OUTPUTS ACHIEVED26

REFERENCES27

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report describes the database on biomass trade, production, demand, biodiversity proxies that will be used to quantify the causal impacts of non-food biomass trade on biodiversity threat proxies through ex-post econometric assessments. More specifically, these data will allow us to estimate trader stickiness and trade substitution elasticities for selected products, evaluate biodiversity threats related to trade of non-food biomass from land, and assess biodiversity risks related to trade of biomass from sea.

This database will be used as input to the empirical studies on how policy instruments and governance regimes moderate the impacts of land use and land cover change (LULCC), thus identifying leverage points for more effective biodiversity governance. To provide empirical estimates of critical parameters determining potential effects of trade, we use data from both various trading partners and several other publicly available data sources. Data were collected with the focus on the case studies proposed in CLEVER both in terms of countries and supply chains/sectors.

To shed light on specific uses of the data for subsequent CLEVER work, we explain each of the datasets forming the data by the following themes:

- 1) International trade network
- 2) Biodiversity indicators
- 3) Aquaculture expansion and trade
- 4) Land tenure data
- 5) Supply chain governance
- 6) Land supply elasticities

Taking the open (FAIR) data principles, we explain how all data will be stored and how to access them. While some of CLEVER partners already stored on FAIR-compatible data portals (e.g., TRASE platform), we here provide cleaned and organized data to be used in specific deliverables within CLEVER, aiming at providing support for the achievement of further deliverables and enabling access for collected research data used in the scientific CLEVER project publications.

INTRODUCTION

International trade in bio-based products can have positive and negative impacts on biodiversity. Negative impacts arise if trade drives land cover change in ecologically sensitive world regions (Chaudhary & Kastner, 2016; Chaudhary & Brooks, 2019). But trade can also protect and enhance biodiversity when it leads to a more efficient allocation of land and other natural resources via the exploitation of local comparative advantages (Baylis et al., 2021; Cherniwchan et al., 2017).

Addressing the trade-biodiversity challenge requires a thorough understanding of the trade-induced threats and the potential beneficial impacts of trade on biodiversity. A comprehensive database on biomass trade, production, demand, and biodiversity proxies is thus essential to explore these complex mechanisms, identify effective policy options, and, ultimately, produce a more holistic, cross-sectoral and transnational perspective on this trade-biodiversity relationship. In fact, recent policy efforts such as the EUDR and EU-Mercosur highlight the relevance of considering both supply and demand when scrutinizing the linkages between trade and biodiversity (European Commission, 2023). This deliverable contributes to building such a database and enables future investigations into positive and negative impacts arising from linkages between trade and biodiversity.

This database consolidates information on the following themes: international trade networks, biodiversity indicators, aquaculture expansion and trade, land tenure, supply chain governance, land supply elasticities. Specifically, it includes data on the trade interconnectedness of countries and pinpointing how strategic interventions to harness this network for enhanced systemic change. This database also offers comprehensive details on publicly sourced biodiversity indicators. Another part of the data organized encapsulates global aquaculture production and trade, coupled with specific trade policy measures, including tariff and non-tariff measures (NTMs). We also provide data on land tenure, with particular emphasis on Brazil. The database further integrates data concerning the soy supply chain in Brazil, analyzing the nexus between soy exports and municipal-scale deforestation, as well as providing measures of the geographic mobility of traders, often referred to as 'stickiness'. Finally, the database presents data on land supply elasticity across tropical regions globally.

The database is available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8304443>. This accompanying report elaborates on the data details and accompanies the database as the main project deliverable.

OBJECTIVES

In this report, we document a database that will serve as input for CLEVER objective II “provide empirical evidence for causal relationships between value chain governance initiatives and biodiversity impacts as well as related policy spillovers”. We aim to:

- Provide a **database on biomass trade, production, demand, biodiversity proxies**. This should serve as an input to guide CLEVER members to both produce variables in their respective work.
- Provide a **cross-theme overview on potential hypotheses that can be explored with the database**. This includes organizing the database into datasets per themes in order to organize different aspects of future CLEVER work as well as identifying empirical opportunities.

METHODS

To create a comprehensive database on biomass trade, production, demand, biodiversity proxies, a series of procedures were followed. The initial step involved identifying potential publicly available datasets that contained relevant information on these topics. Several reputable sources were explored, such as the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), World Bank, United Nations Commodity Trade Statistics Database (UN Comtrade), and national statistical agencies of the countries used as case studies in CLEVER. Once the potential datasets were identified, a filtering process was implemented based on CLEVER objectives. This step ensured that only datasets directly aligned with the research questions and goals were included in the final database. After the filtering process, data collection started. This involved accessing the selected datasets and extracting the relevant variables and observations. Examples of public datasets that was included in the database are FAOSTAT, MAPBIOMAS, TRASE, among others. Once retrieved, the data was organized for use in CLEVER. This involved cleaning the data to remove any inconsistencies, standardizing variables, and ensuring compatibility across different datasets. The collected information was then structured in a database format, enabling efficient storage, retrieval, and manipulation of data during the empirical analyses. Furthermore, to facilitate future CLEVER work, the different datasets were categorized into themes. In the following section, we provide detailed information about each dataset, including data sources, units of measurement, spatiotemporal coverage, and hypotheses that can be tested using them.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section describes databases containing information that will be used to quantify the causal impacts of non-food biomass trade on biodiversity threat proxies through ex-post econometric assessments. Below, we outline all datasets and their respective data sources per theme.

1. International trade network

Exploring the international trade network holds significant importance as it provides valuable insights into the structure of global trade and the varying levels of connectivity among countries (Puma et al., 2015; Torreggiani et al., 2018). Analyzing the connectivity measures of the international trade network enables further investigation into the resilience of a country's trade system (Kummu et al., 2020). Countries that are highly connected and play pivotal roles within the network are likely to have more robust and diversified trade relationships. These countries can leverage their strong network positions to adapt to changes in global trade conditions, navigate economic shocks more effectively, and explore new trading opportunities. On the other hand, countries with limited connectivity may face challenges in diversifying their trade partners and have higher vulnerability to trade disruptions.

Moreover, the connectivity measures can shed light on the interplay between trade agreements, multilateral environmental agreements, and agricultural trade integration. By examining the layering of these agreements and their relationship with the integration of agricultural trade, researchers can gain insights into the effectiveness and impact of these agreements on trade flows among their signatories, for instance (Beghin &, 2021). This analysis can provide valuable information for policymakers seeking to enhance regional trade cooperation and promote sustainable agricultural practices.

Furthermore, studying integration into the trade network, as informed by connectivity measures, allows for exploring relationships with other relevant variables of interest. Researchers can investigate the association between trade integration and factors such as economic growth, income inequality, technological diffusion, or environmental sustainability. By examining these relationships, future studies can uncover valuable insights into the complex dynamics between international trade, socioeconomic factors, and environmental outcomes. In fact, using calculated connectivity measures offer researchers a comprehensive understanding of how individual countries participate in the network and the extent to which they are connected to other countries, enabling the identification of potential trade-driven leverage points toward sustainable transformation.

The data presented here is extensively explained in Jafari et al. (2023). More specifically, this dataset uses information from the FAOSTAT database concerning the international bilateral trade of food and agricultural products. The analysis focuses on snapshots of global trade involving 190 countries, specifically examining the years 1995, 2007, 2013, and 2019. The selection of these specific years serves distinct purposes: 1995 corresponds to the establishment of the World Trade Organization (WTO), 2007 marks the onset of the global food price crisis and predates the financial crisis, 2013 represents a period when the growth of global food and agricultural trade had already reached a plateau, and 2019 represents the most recent year for which data was accessible at the time of the analysis. The connectivity measures were separately calculated in the dimensions of betweenness, closeness, clustering, eigenvector, indegree and instrength, and second-order connectivity (for more details see Jafari et al., 2023).

In each folder of the file “International_trade_network” on Zenodo, there are different Excel files related to the connectivity of individual countries in the trade network when viewed from different perspectives. We provide various measures of connectivity in the agri-food sector’s trade network, considering different trade perspectives. To gain insights into the extensive margin, we examine the trade participation network (TPN), which indicates whether countries at the aggregate agri-food sector level engage in trade with each other or not. Additionally, we analyze the trade participation intensity network (TPIN), which reveals the number of traded commodities among nations. The former provides information on the extensive margin, market diversification, while the latter considers both commodity and market diversification, i.e., the number of active trade links. For insights into the network of trade values, we examine the trade intensity network (TIN), which shows the value of trade among nations.

2. Biodiversity indicators

Regarding biodiversity indicators, we identify several well-established and more recently developed datasets, metrics, and indices representing global biodiversity patterns as well as the level of human impact on biodiversity. We provide an overview of these publicly available global datasets, metrics, or indices (**Table 1**) as a complementary resource to the mapped regional indicators in Deliverable 2.2. These global data may help map and potentially compare baseline levels of biodiversity with those used in D2.2, as well as provide country level data on broader proxies such as human footprints, habitat availabilities, or overall intactness of ecosystems. As also presented in Deliverable 2.1 “Literature review and conceptual framework on mechanisms of how biomass trade affects biodiversity” here we include this table as a non-exhaustive overview of currently available biodiversity metrics and indices. These are all publicly available data, already available through their respective sources (see References).

Table 1. Currently available biodiversity metrics or indices developed by a variety of academic, non-governmental, and corporate sources. Adapted and updated from (IEEP et al., 2021).

Biodiversity metric or indicator	Author(s)/ Reference	Spatial scale	Temporal scale	Description	Class
Biodiversity Habitat Index (BHI) (v2)	(Harwood et al., 2022) Available at: https://doi.org/10.25919/3j75-f539	Global (30arc-second)	2000, 2005, 2010, 2015, and 2020	<p>The BHI estimates the level of species diversity expected to be retained within any given spatial unit (e.g., a country, a broad ecosystem type, or the globe). It is estimated as a function of the unit's area, connectivity, and integrity of natural ecosystems by using remote sensing data and macroecological modelling.</p> <p>It can be expressed as the effective amount of habitat remaining within a unit (e.g., with a score of 100 indicating that a country has experienced no habitat loss or degradation, and 0 a complete loss), or as the proportion of habitat that will result in a proportion of species avoiding extinction in the long-term.</p> <p>It can be used as a conservation-prioritization tool by countries, or as a tool to monitor and report past-to-present trends in expected persistence of species diversity.</p>	Index
Ecosystem Integrity Index (EII)	(Hill et al., 2022) (pre-print)	Global (1km ²)	Not applicable	<p>The EII is an index which incorporates measures of ecosystem integrity via three components: structure, composition, and function. These are measured against a natural, "potential" baseline using a scale of 0-1.</p> <p>Can be used by countries or businesses to establish a baseline and monitor progress towards biodiversity goals or targets.</p>	Index

Biodiversity metric or indicator	Author(s)/ Reference	Spatial scale	Temporal scale	Description	Class
Species Habitat Index (SHI)	(Jetz et al., 2012) Available at: https://epi.yale.edu/epi-results/2020/component/shi	Global (country-level)	2001-2019	<p>The SHI measures the proportion of suitable habitats for a country's species that remain intact, relative to a baseline of 2001. It can be calculated for a single species, but is also aggregated into a single score, with species weighted according to the proportion of their global range found in a given country. The SHI serves as a proxy for potential species extinctions, and similarly as the BHI, a score of 100 indicates no habitat loss since 2001, and 0 complete habitat loss.</p> <p>It is a part of the Map of Life data infrastructure of Yale University.</p> <p>It can be used to compare progress across countries.</p>	Index
Global Areas of Habitat (AoH)	(Lumbierres et al., 2022) Available at: https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.02v6wwq48	Global (100m)	2019/2020 (based on data from 2005-2018)	<p>Provides a global map of Areas of Habitat (i.e., habitats available to species within their associated ranges) for 5,481 terrestrial mammal and 10,651 terrestrial bird species.</p> <p>These data can be used for creating global baseline-maps of species (potential) richness.</p>	Dataset
Living Planet Index	(Collen et al., 2009) Available at: https://www.livingplanetindex.org/	Global (point records)	1970-2018 (note variation in time-series across populations; most records cover 6-10 years of population data)	<p>A measure that aggregates and summarizes vertebrate species population sizes from 5,230 species in terrestrial, freshwater, and marine habitats. Using the year 1970 as a baseline, it indicates overall trends of species abundance. It is also possible to subset for only farmland-specialist species.</p> <p>The LPI can be used to understand trends in species populations and the method has been used to produce national-level indices.</p>	Index

Biodiversity metric or indicator	Author(s)/ Reference	Spatial scale	Temporal scale	Description	Class
Biodiversity Intactness Index (BII)	(Phillips et al., 2021) Available at: https://www.nhm.ac.uk/our-science/data/biodiversity-indicators/biodiversity-intactness-index-data	Global	Not applicable	<p>The BII is an indicator that measures ecological change in response to human pressures. It is estimated as the percent original number and abundance of species that remains despite these pressures. In other words, it is a composite measure of mean abundance, species richness, and community similarity to that of an “undisturbed” area, measuring the relative “intactness” of nature in different land-use types around the world. It can be averaged across areas, e.g., countries, regions, etc.</p> <p>It uses data from the PREDICTS project (Projecting Responses of Ecological Diversity in Changing Terrestrial Systems), which includes over 54,000 species of birds, mammals, plants, fungi, and insects. Differences in sampling across taxa are statistically accounted for.</p> <p>The BII can be used as an overall indicator for global biodiversity targets, as a baseline to quantify biodiversity losses, as a way to project changes in biodiversity in the future, and as a way to compare the impacts of different crops on biodiversity.</p>	Index

Biodiversity metric or indicator	Author(s)/ Reference	Spatial scale	Temporal scale	Description	Class
Human Appropriation of Net-Primary Production (HANPP)	(Haberl et al., 2014; Kastner et al., 2022) Available at: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7313791	Global (5 arc minutes)	1910-2010	<p>HANPP is a measure of the proportion of terrestrial Net Primary Productivity (NPP) that humans consume or “appropriate”. It is measured in units of carbon per year and is the sum of two subcategories: HANPP_{luc} and HANPP_{harv}. HANPP_{harv} is the quantity of carbon in biomass extracted (harvested) by humans or consumed by their livestock per year, including crops, timber, harvested crop residues, forest slash, forages grazed by livestock, and also biomass lost to human-induced fires. HANPP_{luc} denotes alterations in NPP resulting from human-induced land use change, such as the conversion of forest to cropland or infrastructure land. Most recently reconstructed by Kastner et al. (2022).</p> <p>HANPP and its components can also be expressed as the annual percentage of the potential NPP.</p> <p>It can be used as an indicator of human impacts on nature over time.</p>	Dataset
Global Biodiversity Score	(Berger et al., 2021)	Not applicable	Not Applicable	<p>A tool developed to estimate corporate biodiversity footprints. It was developed in cooperation with businesses and financial institutions as well as academics, NGOs and others. It assesses impacts of economic activities across their supply chain, and ecosystem intactness is expressed in a 0-100% scale using the unit of mean species abundance per km² (MSAkm²).</p>	Method/metric proposal and (paid) subscription software

Biodiversity metric or indicator	Author(s)/ Reference	Spatial scale	Temporal scale	Description	Class
Biodiversity Impact Metric	(University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership (CISL), 2020)	Not applicable	Not applicable	A tool developed for corporate businesses to evaluate the level of risk in their agricultural-related supply chains. It is based on three factors, 1) the land area (how many hectares are under production?), 2) quantity impacted (what proportion of biodiversity has been lost through production?), and 3) biodiversity importance (what is the relative global importance of the biodiversity in a particular area?). These three factors are multiplied, which yield a measure of “weighted hectares” impacted by biodiversity.	Method for a metric
A practical approach to measuring the biodiversity impacts of land conversion	(Durán et al., 2020)	Not applicable (adaptable to multiple scales as it relates to land-use data)	Not applicable (adaptable to multiple scales as it relates to land-use data)	A methodological framework based on publicly available data that relates specific land-use changes to species-specific habitats and the likelihood of their populations’ persistence. Importantly, it allows for incorporating cumulative, nonlinear impacts on species’ persistence (i.e. including historical land-use changes) by considering proportional habitat loss compared to species-specific AOH baselines. It may still omit effects on species from habitat fragmentation. Can be used to quantify impacts of human drivers on biodiversity.	Method for a metric

Biodiversity metric or indicator	Author(s)/ Reference	Spatial scale	Temporal scale	Description	Class
Species Threat Abatement and Restoration (STAR) metric and the Integrated Biodiversity Assessment Tool (IBAT)	<p>(<i>Integrated Biodiversity Assessment Tool (IBAT)</i>, n.d.)</p> <p>Available at: https://www.ibat-alliance.org/sample-downloads?tab=gis-downloads&anchor_id=resource-header</p>	Global (50 km or 5km res)	Not applicable	<p>A metric that quantifies the contributions from mitigating or “abating” threats and restoring habitats in specific places towards reducing species extinction risk. It is derived from the IUCN’s (International Union for Conservation of Nature) Red List, species’ Areas of Habitat, and land cover maps (using a backcasting to model pre-human-impact habitats and land cover to establish a baseline).</p> <p>The STAR score varies from 0 (Least Concern) to 100 (Near Threatened), 200 (Vulnerable), 300 (Endangered), and 400 (Critically Endangered). STAR values across species represents the global threat abatement effort needed for all species to become Least Concern.</p> <p>The IBAT tool and software is geared towards businesses to help them identify assess, reduce, and manage biodiversity extinction risk in specific places (e.g., locations where they produce or source products from)</p>	<p>1) Publicly available dataset (at 50km res)</p> <p>2) Paid software subscription that provides data at 5km2 res and guidance for planning corporate responsibility</p>

3. Aquaculture expansion and trade

The impacts of non-tariff measures on global freshwater aquaculture production has great potential for global food provision and environmental protection. This sector and especially the freshwater aquaculture subsector have grown at an impressive rate in the last decades (Naylor et al, 2021). The majority of aquaculture products are destined for domestic markets, however, an increasing quantity is oriented for export. Previous studies suggest that international trade is the main driver of aquaculture production (Asche et al, 2016; Naylor et al, 2021; Mahfuz, 2006).

Trade policy measures such as tariff and non-tariff measures (NTMs) have an important role on aquaculture development. NTMs include both technical and non-technical regulations and standards designed to protect consumer health and safeguard the environment, which can determine “what and how firms produce” (Movchain et al, 2019). While applied tariffs for seafood are relatively low (~ 14%) and have been reduced or stayed at zero (FAO, 2022), NTMs have played a important role in the trade-environment relationship in the seafood sector (Asche et al, 2016). Besides increasing cost of compliance for producers, NTMs may also cause procedural obstacles such as non-transparency or discriminatory behaviors (UNCTAD, 2012).

In this dataset, we are interested in i) NTMs applied by a country, and ii) NTMs that a country might have to face. These data can be used to test different hypotheses on how and under which conditions NTMs can increase or decrease domestic production of aquaculture and affect the environment.

While the optimal level for tariff is zero, we expect that the impacts of NTMs are complex and determining an optimal level of NTMs for sustainable aquaculture development is challenging. These data will be used to estimate the effects of NTMs that countries apply and face in freshwater aquaculture production by adopting a fixed-effects model using a panel of 181 countries between 1996 and 2020. We include control variables such as population, GDP per capita, share of urban population, cumulative number of annually effective trade agreements, and applied tariff for seafood products. To address the heterogeneity effect of NTMs across countries, we plan to further apply quantile regression with fixed effects.

The table below provides details on the “Aquaculture_expansion_trade” dataset on Zenodo, which includes country-year information on aquaculture production and consumption, tariff and non-tariff measures and trade agreements. Each country is identified by its original name and a two-digit code as described in the ISO 3166 international standard.

Variable	Description	Raw data source	Authors' data processing
LogAqua	Annual quantity of freshwater aquaculture production in natural logarithm	FishStatJ	The original data is measured in ‘tonnes of live weight’ and is recorded for various species in marine, brackish, and freshwater environments in each country. We

			aggregate this data to total annual volume from freshwater environment per country.
LogNTM_applied	Cumulative number of NTMs that each country applies annually for product group HS03 "Fish and crustaceans, mollusks and other aquatic invertebrates" in natural logarithm	UNCTAD TRAINS Database	We extract all NTM cases for product group HS03 that have been applied by different countries. We replace EU observations with EU countries with respect to their year of membership. We calculate the cumulative number of effective NTMs applied annually by countries in total and per type of NTMs (e.g., SPS, TBT)
LogNTM_faced	Cumulative number of NTMs that each country faces annually for product group HS03 in natural logarithm	UNCTAD TRAINS Database	The variable "Partner affected by NTM" in the original data contains unidentical subsets of countries (e.g., "World (except Canada)", "Colombia, France, Venezuela"). We transform this variable so that each observation presents a bilateral relationship. We calculate the cumulative number of effective NTMs that each country must face when exporting seafood products.
LogPopulation	Total population in each country in natural logarithm	World Development Indicators	We transform the original data to a panel country-year level.
LogGDPpercap	Per capita values for GDP in current international dollars converted by purchasing power parity conversion factor in natural logarithm	World Development Indicators	We transform the original data to a panel country-year level.
UrbanShare	Percent of total population living in urban areas	World Development Indicators	We transform the original data to a panel country-year level.
CumNoTAs	Cumulative number of effective trade agreements (TAs)	MacMap	We collect all trade agreements applied for each country as an exporter, including inactive and in force TAs. For inactive TAs, we fill in the years the TAs went inactive. Finally, we transform the data to a panel country-year level and calculate the cumulative number of TAs in force annually in each country.
LogTariff	Applied MFN rate (simple average with ad valorem equivalents %) that each country applies for product group HS03	WTOStats	We replace observation "EU" in the original data with EU countries considering their year of membership. We then transform the dataset to a panel country-year level.

4. Land tenure

Land tenure, which governs the ownership and use of land and its natural resources, is considered an important indirect driver of land use change and its impacts on biodiversity (Robinson et al., 2018; Tseng et al., 2021). In parallel, agricultural-trade-related land-use decision-making occurs at the property/parcel level. However, spatially explicit, parcel-level data on land tenure are scarce, rarely publicly available, or accessible at prohibitively high costs. Hence, land tenure data is explored in only of the CLEVER case studies - Brazil.

In Brazil, a global biodiversity and deforestation hotspot, nature conservation efforts in the past decades have primarily focused on curbing deforestation. Among these efforts, the rural environmental cadaster of land (Cadastro Ambiental Rural – CAR) was created as a tool for monitoring and enforcing existing environmental policies, with particular emphasis in the Amazon and Cerrado biomes where land tenure configurations are often less known.

As a result of this massive effort to self-report, as well as systematize already demarcated and titled lands (e.g., private and public lands, alongside protected areas and indigenous lands), Brazil holds a highly comprehensive parcel-level dataset on different categories of land tenure across the country. These data can be related to any number of spatial, environmental variables, including biodiversity.

Figure 1. Map of summarized land tenure categories in Brazil. Border lines indicate Brazil's biomes.

These parcel-level data were compiled and spatial overlaps were harmonized via a prioritization process by Imaflora (de Freitas et al., 2018; Imaflora et al., 2018), where they report 18 categories of land ownership. We recategorized these 18 land tenure

categories into 7 categories that are similarly found across other global tenure systems: undesignated public lands (lands belonging to the state but under no formal designation or title), rural settlements (lands with rural settlers, but with little guaranteed property rights), private lands, protected areas (for both strict protection and for sustainable use), indigenous lands, communal, and quilombola lands (lands belonging to descendants of African slaves in Brazil). For this deliverable, we provide these data in both gridded and vector formats (.gri and .shp) in the dataset “Land_tenure” on Zenodo.

These data can be potentially related to a number of hypotheses in the project. As we aim to conduct analyses with the highest level of spatial detail as possible, first steps will involve relating these property-level data to likely origins of different supply chains (e.g., soy production), or compliance to different policies or interventions at these local scales.

5. Supply chain governance

Evaluating supply chain initiatives is crucial for effectively addressing environmental impacts and promoting sustainability. Understanding the importance of evaluating these initiatives allows policymakers and stakeholders to develop targeted strategies that mitigate negative environmental consequences and promote positive change in specific supply chains (Garrett et al., 2021; Lambin et al., 2018). To provide empirical estimates of critical parameters determining potential effects associated with trade governance interventions, we use data from various trading partners, focusing specifically on the soy supply chains in Brazil. Our plan is to conduct studies using quasi-experimental evaluation methods with high spatiotemporal resolution trade data provided by our CLEVER partner SEI via their TRASE platform, as well as several other publicly available data sources. In this deliverable, we detail two aspects of supply chain that will be further investigated within CLEVER: international trade rules and trader stickiness.

International trade rules play a significant role in shaping environmental policies and practices due to their potential of either support or hinder environmental protection efforts in producing regions. Evaluating the impact of different rules can help to identify areas where adjustments or improvements can be made to promote sustainable practices and reduce negative environmental impacts associated with trade. Consumers worldwide are increasingly concerned about deforestation-linked agricultural commodities and have pressured towards sustainable products. Although putting pressure on companies to ensure environmentally responsible supply chains, consumer preferences are not homogeneous across the globe and heterogeneous levels of acceptability in international markets do exist (Pendrill et al., 2019; Hoang and Kanemoto, 2021; Hong et al., 2022). This heterogeneity encourages some producers to resort to non-sustainable agricultural practices.

International trade may lead to production decisions that result in environmental harms if consumers in importing countries do not demand sustainable farming practices and/or if the environmental regulations are weak. A rise in importers’ demand triggers an increase in production by exporters (Eaton and Kortum, 2002) which can lead to either agricultural intensification or extensification (Tilman et al., 2011; Dias et al., 2016). Whether and to what extent this enhanced production is driven by improving productivity or using additional land may be greatly influenced by the demand side conditions in

importing countries (Ericksen, 2008; Henders and Ostwald, 2014; Hong et al., 2022). Considering the last decades of the production of soybean in Brazil, extensification has been a more pronounced factor (see Song et al., 2021). While producers can engage in activities like forest clearance or the replacement of other agricultural uses (e.g., pasture) to expand soybean plantations, the former is often less costly, mainly because of weak property rights definition and protection in public lands and imperfect enforcement of environmental regulations (Pendrill et al., 2022).

To further investigate specific supply chain governance initiatives, we focus in the soy supply chain in Brazil, where the example of the Soy Moratorium has illustrated relevant mechanisms to be explored (see Gibbs et al., 2015; Soterroni et al., 2019; Heilmayr et al., 2020). In dataset “Supply_chain_governance_Trade” on Zenodo, we detail information at the municipality-year level from 2004 to 2018 in Brazil. More specifically, these data encompass information on soy trade, deforestation, land cover measures, gross domestic product (GDP soybean production (hectares), population density, value added of agriculture in gross domestic product (GDP), value added of industry in GDP, average annual temperature (C°), average annual wind speed (m/s), price effects associated with soybean and cattle production activities, the degree of international market participation at the municipal level, and environmental enforcement measured by fines released by IBAMA. All these data will serve as outcome variables, instrumental variables, variables of interest, or control variables. All sources are identified in the reference list. This dataset is presented in a municipality-year panel, where each municipality is identified by a unique 7-digit code and its official name, according to the 2021 data from the Brazilian Territorial Division (DTB) of the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE). The table below outlines the data covering all Brazilian municipalities from 2004-2018.

Variables	Description	Raw data source
Soy_EU	Soy exports (kg) to EU per municipality <i>i</i> in year <i>t</i> .	TRADE
Soy_China	Soy exports (kg) to China per municipality <i>i</i> in year <i>t</i> .	TRADE
Deforestation	Number of hectares of forest loss by municipality <i>i</i> in year <i>t</i> .	MAPBIOMAS
SurroundingDeforestation	Number of hectares of forest loss by neighbors of the neighboring municipalities of municipality <i>i</i> in year <i>t</i> .	MAPBIOMAS
EU_TradeExposure	Interaction term between market share (%) of exporting countries other than Brazil in the EU soy imports in year <i>t</i> -1 and potential soy yields with high-input level and rainfed all phases (0 to 10000) by municipality <i>i</i> .	FAOSTAT, FAOGAEZ
China_TradeExposure	Interaction term between market share (%) of exporting countries other than Brazil in the Chinese soy imports in year <i>t</i> -1 and potential soy yields with high-input level and rainfed all phases (0 to 10000) by municipality <i>i</i> .	FAOSTAT, FAOGAEZ
Forest_Soy	Number of hectares of land conversion of forestland to soybean plantations per municipality <i>i</i> in year <i>t</i> .	MAPBIOMAS
Pasture_Soy	Number of hectares of land conversion of pasture to soybean plantations per municipality <i>i</i> in year <i>t</i> .	MAPBIOMAS

Soycrop_cover	Number of hectares of soybeans plantations cover per municipality i in year t.	MAPBIOMAS
PopulationDensity	Population density (total inhabitants/km ²) per municipality i in year t.	IBGE
Temperature	Average temperature (C ^o) per municipality i in year t. We calculate annual averages of 6-hour intervals measures.	INPE
Wind_speed	Average wind speed (m/s) per municipality i in year t. We calculate annual averages of 6-hour intervals measures.	INPE
EnvFines	Number of IBAMA deforestation-related environmental fines per municipality i in year t.	IBAMA
SoyPriceExposure	Interaction term between the average export price (USD/ton) of soybean in Brazil per year t and the share (%) of municipal area used as farmland for soybean plantations in 2004 per municipality i.	FAOSTAT, MAPBIOMAS, IBGE
CattlePriceExposure	Interaction term between the average export price (USD/ton) of cattle in Brazil per year t and the share (%) of municipal area used as pasture lands in 2004 per municipality i.	FAOSTAT, MAPBIOMAS, IBGE
ExportsExposure	Interaction term between the annual average selling exchange rate from USD to BRL per year t and the number of companies that are officially registered as exporters in 2004 per municipality i.	Central Bank and Ministry of Economy in Brazil
ImportsExposure	Interaction term between the annual average selling exchange rate from USD to BRL per year t and the number of companies that are officially registered as importers in 2004 per municipality i.	Central Bank and Ministry of Economy in Brazil
ExplmpExposure	Interaction term between the annual average selling exchange rate from USD to BRL per year t and the number of companies that are officially registered as both importers and exporters in 2004 per municipality i	Central Bank and Ministry of Economy in Brazil

Another key factor to consider while analysing supply chain governance is the concept of trader stickiness, which refers to the tendency of traders to maintain long-term relationships with specific suppliers (Reis et al., 2020). The stickiness of traders can serve as a potential leverage point for protecting the environment within supply chains. By fostering long-term relationships with suppliers who adhere to sustainable practices, traders can incentivize and drive positive change throughout the supply chain. Understanding the dynamics of trader stickiness and its influence on sourcing decisions provides valuable insights for designing initiatives that encourage and reward sustainability.

Stickiness can be explored here as the degree of geographic mobility of traders across individual commodity sourcing locations, which can likely influence the impact of sustainability-oriented value chain governance initiatives and policies (see Reis et al., 2020). Mobile traders can meet newly imposed sustainability criteria by moving to sourcing regions with high levels of producer compliance. Such a shift might be convenient, for instance, when due diligence legislation is enforced in export destinations

and producer compliance varies regionally. The propensity of traders to transition to new sourcing regions hinges on their anticipated profits and sunk costs, such as investments in local transportation or processing infrastructure. These costs could potentially sway the balance in favor of sticking to established sourcing patterns.

In order to investigate the role of traders' stickiness on shifts in agricultural commodity sourcing and therefore on the environment in producing regions, we organize data on traders flows in the Brazilian soy market. Our data is drawn from the TRASE database (trade flow information from sourcing locations to traders and from traders to export destinations), augmented with other sources to identify characteristics of sourcing locations, traders, and export destinations. Specific environmental policies in Brazil will be further identified, but are based on spatially explicit soy traders' municipal exposure. The stickiness measure was based on the authors' own calculations, using equations explained by Reis et al. (2020). We decompose the stickiness measure to gauge how sticky soy traders are in their supply chain in terms of shifting their (1) sourcing municipalities and (2) destination countries.

Three specific pieces of information is worthy mentioning. First, stickiness is calculated on an annual basis. Second, missing values indicate that the trader did not export soy when considering the two time periods. Third, all four measures are indexes ranging from 0 to 1 - where 0 implies that the entire trade network changed completely, and 1 means that the entire trade network remained entirely unchanged over the assessed period. In the dataset "Supply_chain_governance_Stickiness" on Zenodo, we provide four trader-year level stickiness measures, using data provided by TRASE: (1) stickiness in terms of sourcing municipalities, based on binary changes for each soy trader i in Brazil; (2) stickiness in terms of sourcing municipalities, based on volume changes for each soy trader i in Brazil; (3) stickiness in terms of destination countries, based on binary changes for each soy trader i in Brazil; and (4) stickiness in terms of destination countries, based on volume changes for each soy trader i in Brazil.

6. Land supply elasticities

Land-driven biodiversity loss depends on how the market for land is governed. In the context of global economic models, the supply and demand dynamics of land for agricultural production and its influence on agricultural practices can contribute to deforestation and habitat degradation, leading to biodiversity loss (Ceddia et al., 2013; Hertel, 2011). As demand for land increases, particularly for agriculture (crop production or pastures), and the price of land rises, landowners may convert more natural areas or forests into agricultural land if the supply is elastic. This conversion, often in the form of deforestation, can result in significant biodiversity loss. For example, in regions with high biodiversity like the Amazon in South America and the Congo Basin in Central Africa, an increase in agricultural commodity prices has been shown to lead to larger areas of forest being converted into agricultural land.

The strength and type of governance in a region can also play a significant role in influencing land supply and consequently biodiversity loss (Angelsen, 2010; Lambin et al., 2014). Strong environmental governance could lead to the creation of protected areas, restrictions on deforestation, or sustainable land management practices, all of

which could help conserve biodiversity. However, poor governance, high levels of corruption, or a lack of environmental regulations could lead to more land being unsustainably exploited, leading to greater biodiversity loss. Furthermore, stringent conservation policies can sometimes lead to spillover effects, causing increased pressure on land and resources in surrounding jurisdictions, potentially leading to biodiversity loss there.

Moreover, when thinking about land supply for agricultural expansion, two critical factors emerge: the suitability of the soil and the potential crop yields. The better the soil is for growing crops, the more likely it is to be converted into farmland. This suitability is determined by the physical and chemical properties of the soil. The potential yield of a plot of land refers to the maximum amount of crop it can produce under ideal conditions. Higher potential yield makes a plot of land more desirable for farming. However, if the potential yield is low, farmers might feel the need to clear more land for farming to meet their production targets. This would inevitably lead to larger-scale deforestation and habitat loss.

We then collected data on land supply elasticities to be further used in CLEVER future work. These data can provide relevant information that would help to calibrate land use change processes in CGE models, such as GLOBIOM. Further methodological details on how the data is constructed can be found in Miranda and Börner (2023).

The dataset “Land_supply_elasticities” on Zenodo focuses on the land supply elasticities using the unit of observation as agroecological zones (AEZ) within national boundaries. The data sources include the Global AEZ (GAEZ) and the Database of Global Administrative Areas, and the European Space Agency's Climate Change Initiative land cover data. Only tropical regions are considered, so from the 876 AEZ-country regions were identified, only 267 mesoregions are considered. Agricultural land was measured as the share of the total land in an AEZ-country unit to create the land supply elasticities. A set of covariates on the socioeconomic, biophysical, and governance components of land rents was also used.

CONCLUSION

This deliverable detailed the database on biomass trade, production, demand, and biodiversity proxies. This database includes different datasets on the themes of international trade network, biodiversity indicators, aquaculture production and trade, land tenure, supply chain governance, and land supply. These datasets are divided into themes due to their distinct spatiotemporal coverage. Among other goals, these data will be used within CLEVER as input in further deliverables focused on estimating trader stickiness, trade substitution elasticities, and biodiversity risks related to non-food biomass trade.

PROJECT OUTPUTS ACHIEVED

This deliverable provides details on Work Package 3 - D3.1 Database on biomass trade, production, demand, and biodiversity proxies. Along with Deliverable D2.2 (Biodiversity Indicator Database), these data will be used to explore CLEVER objectives:

- I. Improve our understanding of how biomass trade is linked to biodiversity impacts and co-benefits in exporting and importing regions.*
- II. Provide empirical evidence for causal relationships between value chain governance initiatives and biodiversity impacts as well as related policy spillovers.*

More specifically, this deliverable will be further explored in Work Package 2 - D2.3 Biodiversity impact estimates and in Work Package 3 - D3.2 Estimated trade substitution elasticities; D3.3 Quantified ex-post impacts of trade in terrestrial biomass on biodiversity; D3.4 Quantified ex-post biodiversity threats of trade in biomass from sea.

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